

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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о достижении конкретных целей продаж и достижении прибыли компании, а также автоматизирует процесс продаж, что сокращает человеческий труд в компании, что позволяет компании инвестировать в другие области. Таким образом, данная статья покажет, что действующая CRM-система является неотъемлемой частью работы всех современных отделов продаж компании.

Ключевые слова: CRM-система, Отдел продаж, автоматизация продаж, CRM-инструменты, Рост выручки, Оптимизация продаж, Конверсия лидов, Удержание клиентов.

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the article was to show that the operational CRM system greatly helps the company's revenue growth by automating the sales department process. Therefore, in order to fully cover this selected hypothesis, primary research was first conducted, the opinions of the sales department employee and the company owner about the important factors of operational CRM were determined through a questionnaire form. Through secondary research, we showed with clear analytical figures that after the introduction of CRM to large companies by the Aberdeen research company, the flow of leads increased, the flow of quality customers was ensured, and the stability of the flow was ensured. The overall research results revealed that the operational CRM system provides efficiency to the company's sales representatives and sets clear goals.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Operational Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems are integral to modern sales departments, serving as the backbone for managing customer interactions, streamlining processes, and enhancing overall sales performance. Buttle and Maklan emphasize that these systems encompass sales force automation, marketing automation, and service automation, each playing a pivotal role in optimizing sales operations.

Sales force automation (SFA) is a core component of operational CRM, designed to automate various stages of the sales cycle. Tanner, Ahearne, Leigh, Mason, and Moncrief highlight that SFA manages activities from initial contact entry to converting prospects into clients, ensuring efficient tracking of customer interactions and reducing redundant efforts. By implementing SFA, sales teams can enhance productivity and focus more on building relationships rather than administrative tasks.

Marketing automation within operational CRM focuses on streamlining marketing processes to increase effectiveness. Nilashi, Abumalloh, Samad, Alrizq, Alyami, and Alghamdi argue that this includes automating repetitive tasks such as sending targeted emails or managing social media campaigns, aiming to nurture leads and convert them into customers. By leveraging marketing automation, sales departments can ensure consistent messaging and timely follow-ups, which are crucial for maintaining customer engagement.

Service automation is another critical aspect, concentrating on improving customer service efficiency. According to Buttle and Maklan, service automation provides support through multiple channels like phone, email, and self-service portals, ensuring that customer issues are addressed promptly. Effective service automation leads to higher customer satisfaction, which directly impacts customer retention and loyalty.

The integration of these components within an operational CRM system provides a comprehensive view of each customer, enabling sales departments to tailor their strategies effectively. Tanner et al. note that by analyzing data collected through these systems, businesses can identify patterns and trends that inform decision-making, leading to improved sales performance.

In conclusion, operational CRM systems are indispensable tools for sales departments aiming to enhance efficiency, improve customer interactions, and drive sales growth. As Nilashi et al. emphasize, by automating key processes and providing valuable insights, these systems empower sales teams to perform at their best in a competitive marketplace.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for studying the role of operational CRM systems in sales departments relies on both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data is collected through surveys and structured interviews with sales professionals to assess CRM adoption and its impact. Secondary data is gathered from academic journals and industry reports. The collected data is analyzed using statistical techniques to identify patterns, correlations, and performance improvements linked to CRM implementation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Sales teams can focus on high-value operations like prospecting, customer engagement, and closing deals by using Salesforce CRM to automate time-consuming administrative tasks. Studies show that customer

response times are significantly improved, sales cycle times are shortened by 29%, and manual work is reduced by 75%. These improvements in metrics also translate into measurable revenue growth, with monthly revenue increasing by 30% and quarterly sales growth increasing by 140%. Businesses that use Salesforce are seeing an increase in closed deals, along with increased customer value through personalized sales strategies. [1]. Attracting new consumer is more important for each business company, so saving the consumer is much cheaper rather than converting new ones. Selling to an existing customer has a 60-70% success rate, while selling to a new prospect has a 5-20% chance. It can be difficult to ensure that salespeople follow through on different types of deals. CRM systems keep sales reps more focused by reminding them of deadlines and tasks that need to be completed during the closing process, sending reminders about required documents, and enabling sales reps to stay in touch with products and features that meet customer needs. [2]

Operational CRM helps align the goals of all teams in a company. Operations CRM collects lead data from the marketing department, directly links it to the goals of the sales department, and transfers information about current and prospective customers to the service department. Through this process, adapting CRM to different departments in the company helps automate processes and improves the overall customer experience. This then allows the company to spend less labor, i.e., reduce manual labor, and invest in areas where the company needs to grow. We can see how a CRM system automates processes in the example of the sales department (Figure 1):

Figure 1. CRM system automation on the example of a sales department.

According to Aberdeen research, sales automation offers a hugely differentiating opportunity and insight. "Best-in-class" companies using sales automation have seen a 217% return on their investment to date. The company's research shows that additional investment in CRM has yielded positive real-world business results:

- The company delivered 52% more proposals, quotes, or RFP responses to prospects.
- Sales quotations were 32% higher for the team (62% vs. 47%)
- Lead conversion rates were 23% higher (33% vs. 27%) [3] (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Additional investments in CRM can yield positive results in real business.

When analyzing the primary and secondary research conducted, first of all, the interview form responses of an employee who worked as a sales department employee at Pebbles Family Company were focused on, and the main reason for introducing an operational CRM system into the company was that the company was unable to properly capture customer data and was unable to properly utilize incoming leads, resulting in problems such as not being able to reach sales. The responses of the company owner also show that, as a company manager, when analyzing from above, he emphasized that due to the expansion of the company, the number of employees and customers increased, and control over the processes in the company's internal environment was lost. So, to conclude, an increase in the size of a company affects the stable operation of internal processes and the expected results, which is why all large companies or those that want to capture the market need to install operational CRM.

According to the company's salesperson, after the CRM system was installed, customer data management became easier, quickly accessing customer history and segmenting them based on their interests became much easier than before. Therefore, after this system, all customer data was centralized and all employees had the opportunity to use the updated database. These processes also foster personalized sales after providing the company's sales department with each customer's information, their history, and interests. For example, if the customer information contains English language classes, offers are created that are tailored to the customer's needs and requirements during the sales process. This increases customer loyalty among the company, and the company also improves customer retention. Through the multi-functionality of operational CRM, the number of leads increases and customer retention also increases. It improves constant communication with customers and always reminds them to make sales. The automation of these processes increases the company's performance. According to the company owner, after installing the CRM system, parents will be able to see the learning process of their child, as well as the duration of the course and how much time is left for the payment. That is, with this system, the company provides its clients with convenient tariff purchases, subscriptions, and through this, the company will be able to analyze the automation of sales and regular income.

According to the company's sales department employee's own recommendation and conclusion, the operational CRM system makes the sales process clear, makes working with customers meaningful, because a continuous clear process satisfies the needs of customers and improves the company's performance. According to the opinion and recommendation of the company's CEO, all business owners can save resources and time in their business and increase the sales process by automating internal processes. He also emphasized the need for the business owner to facilitate and automate the first customer payment after installing the CRM system for the first time.

Secondary research shows that companies that implement high-end CRMs have a 217% return on their investment, according to Aberdeen. This research clearly shows that companies that implement sales automation through operational CRMs have a 32% higher conversion rate for their sales teams, for example. Regarding Jaseem Pookandy's research paper, operational CRM system helps the sales department of a company to attract customers, increase their satisfaction and make sales by automating time and tasks. If we look at this in concrete numbers, the operational CRM system installed in the sales department then reduced the company's routine tasks by 75%, and the time spent on the sales process by 29%. This brought 30% more revenue per month for the company. Also, the company has significantly increased the value provided to customers through the automation of sales through this system and personalized sales strategies. Similarly, if we look at primary research, the sales person and CEO of Pebbles Family Company said that the main reason for installing operational CRM in the company was that the company had more than 2000 customers, which led to the number of employees reaching 130. This caused problems in customer retention, implementation of quality sales processes, and internal processes in the company. That's why the company implemented ALFA CRM, which allows sales staff to create a centralized database of all customers, segment them based on their interests and needs, view customer history, and create a centralized sales process. This has helped the company automate the sales process, reduce labor, and make more sales, improving the company's annual revenue and performance.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, an operational CRM system is an important business tool that provides automation of the sales process by organizing and segmenting customer data. Also, according to the analysis of the above research, in today's competitive market, all growing and expanding companies must use a CRM system to optimize internal processes. In addition, an operational CRM system brings quality leads to the company's sales department and increases the company's revenue through a centralized sales strategy.

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